

TITLE

Multiple Classification using Similarity Matching of Products based

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Introduction:

In the present era there is scenario of ecommerce where all the users like retailers and whole sellers are buying and selling the goods frequently across the globe so it has been observed that users has to explore the various types of ecommerce platform before purchasing any required items so this is a kind of present trend so technically here segregation is required to distinguish the items which are displayed on same value at multiple ecommerce platform hence such type of issue required solution at the company level can be resolved through the use of classifiers and label of item class that is specifically based on similarity among the samples used for training a set.

Current Need:

Any store like flipkart, amazon, alibaba, ebay supports towards the selling of their goods and item on this e commerce platform and it might possible to get same price of goods at other platform also therefore segregation of item is required.

Objective:

- To classify the products
- To compare the similar products

Technology Used:

To identify the similarity of items in the ecommerce platform like amazon, flipkart, paytm, myntra, jiomart, alibaba, ebay and also available at the offline mode is a crucial investigation and if someone is doing comparison of goods through the tools and comparative study for the same plays a significant role in this perception therefore here various types of technology comes at back of the mind as follows:

- ^ NN

Machine Learning

Neural network

- SVM
- Classifiers
- Class labels
- Training Sets of data
- RNN
- Python to train the model

Fig1. Similarity of products

Challenges:

Product matching is a difficult task due to the broader spectrum of products, many similar but different products, often missing or incorrect values, and frequent variation in the textual nature of products.

- **Data dispersion:** While some professional and commercial sellers provide valuable information from their item listings, a large majority of midsize and small sellers provide short, and sometimes incomplete descriptions. This results in a severe paucity of data due to missing values that are important for identifying products.

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Duplicate products: Data paucity and misinformation automatically drawn from unstructured or semi-structured sources can result in the same product being created two or more times, called duplicates. Duplicate products are not only one of the biggest sources of bad product experiences, but they also make product matching difficult as there are multiple entities of the same product with overlapping information. Duplicates can have many fatal effects, including preventing machine learning algorithms from discovering important consistencies in product renderings.

- **Single Source Products:** There are many rare products, such as antiques, collectibles, books, sculptures, etc., that are only offered by a private or commercial seller. These products are often called single source products. In such cases, the product description cannot be cross-validated in the absence of alternative sources. This causes a one-time learning problem, which is learning a class from a single tagged example.

- **Product bundles and bundles:** bundles are defined as multiple different products that are bundled together and sold as a single offer. If the offer contains multiples of the same product, these offers are called a batch. They make the data ambiguous, like a number in the product description could be a large quantity or a variation of the product edition. Such product offerings exhibit another level of complexity that requires special treatment or a separate model to identify lots and packages.

- **Extreme Classification:** Traditionally, multi-class classification solutions have been scalable to a few hundred classes. As the number of classes increases, the complexity of time and space increases exponentially as the standard models do not expand. For the task of matching products, the number of products is in the millions, and therefore methods are required that can scale up to a million classes.

- **Open set classification:** The number of classes is usually predefined for classification tasks, and the models are designed to predict one of those predefined classes for a given instance. For the task of matching products, every day new products are created that become part of the inventory increasing the quantity of products daily. It requires frequent retraining of models with newly created products with additional classes or employing models capable of handling invisible products.

Procedure:

We ran a series of experiments on an eBay dataset. The data has been collected over the years, we adapted an open source implementation for our task: <https://github.com/dhwajraj/deep-siamese-text-similarity> and contains millions of products and billions of listings . We divide the data into meta-categories and the models are trained in these categories separately. This partition into categories not only keeps the size of the data at an affordable level given the resources, but also allows us to train the models in parallel so that each category is independent. In this paper, we only report experiments for three categories, namely electronics, apparel, shoes and accessories (CSA) and collectibles as proof of concept. In the following sections, we will briefly explain how this historical data was created.

Results:

Many fasttext models with various combinations of inputs. For all of our models, the embed dimension is set to 300, the learning rate to 0.5, and the number of epochs to 10. The n-gram parameter is set to 3 and provides nice improvements over models without these additional features. . The hierarchical softmax has been used as a loss function.

Conclusion:

We have proposed similarity and classification based approaches to the product matching task. The inputs to our models are a sequence of texts unlike many of the previous studies where more emphasis has been placed on structured text for such tasks. The classification approach based on fastText models can scale up to millions of classes, exceeds the baseline, and is extremely efficient to train. The similarity approach based on the Siamese network uses both article lists and product text. Not only do they further improve accuracy, but they also have the advantage of avoiding frequent retraining. As a by-product, we have also demonstrated the potential of using our models for product deduplication, which we plan to explore further in our future work. Finally, our models can accommodate any information (beyond title, gtin, brand and mpn) easily manageable in textual form. Now we are planning to extend them with image data.

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